

Theoretical Study and Analysis of KBM and SP Method on IADLs in Plasma Considering Electrons and Positrons

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Abstract-*This study uses the Krylov-Bogoliubov-Mitropolsky (KBM) method and the Sagdeev Potential (SP) method to theoretically analyze ion-acoustic double layers (IADLs) in plasma for electrons and positrons. Not only that, it is also valid for static negatively charged dust particles also. For the KBM approach, the profiles of the SP method and the IADLs are painted and examined for additional values of the URD two-temperature electrons and positrons. Analysis reveals that both the particle (electron and positron) considering degenerate state plays a significant role in the construction of "Rarefactive IADLs" in the URD electrons and positrons plasma. The shape and widths of IADLs produced by the KBM approach and the SP method are also compared in the paper.*

Keywords: *Ultra-relativistic particles, Ion-acoustic double layers(IADL), Sagdeev Potential method, Dusty plasma, Krylov-Bogoliubov-Mitropolsky method.*

1.0 Introduction

By accelerating the plasma electrons and ions in opposite directions, a strong electric field across the two oppositely charged layers generates and increases an electric current. The DLs have generated a great deal of attention in astrophysics and can be found in a wide range of plasmas [1]. Ion-acoustic double layers (IADLs) in various plasma systems have attracted the attention of several authors in recent years using reductive perturbation techniques (RPT) and the Sagdeev Potential (SP) method [2-7]. The thermal de Broglie wavelength may match the antiparticle lengths at very low temperatures and high plasma densities. Due to the neighboring particles' wave functions overlapping in these circumstances, quantum phenomena play a significant role. Using the Quantum Hydrodynamic (QHD) model developed by Haas et al., the nonlinear and linear properties of waves in quantum (degenerate) plasma are drastically altered [8]. The significant role of quantum diffraction is studied in both the linear and nonlinear regimes. By ignoring pressure effects for the ions, an equation of state is assumed to apply to a zero-temperature Fermi gas for the electrons in this paper. By roughly rescaling the variable, it is discovered that the no-dimensional parameter H is directly proportional to the effects of quantum diffraction. It is demonstrated that the system permits linear waves, which resemble classical ion-acoustic waves in the limit of tiny H . The quantum plasma is discovered to support waves in the weak nonlinear limit that are described by a deformed Korteweg-de Vries(KdV) equation that rely nontrivial on the quantum parameter H . The system also permits traveling waves that can exhibit periodic patterns in the totally nonlinear regime. The researcher of Haas et al. [8] has inspired many authors to investigate the nonlinear acoustic wave propagation in quantum plasma. Aliand Shukla[9] used a one-dimensional QHD model for a three species quantum plasma to derive a K-dV equation with quantum corrections and explore the nonlinear characteristics of dust acoustic solitary waves. Numerical analysis is used to study the influence of quantum mechanics on the profiles of the width and amplitude of dust

acoustic solitary waves. Although the width decreases for various values of the dimensionless electron quantum parameter H , the soliton's amplitude (voting level) remains constant. Misra and Bhowmik [10] adopted a nonplanar spherical geometry to investigate the nonlinear characteristics of ion-acoustic waves (IAW) in an electron-ion quantum plasma with the effects of quantum corrections. Additionally, they developed the Kadomtsev-Petviashvili (KP) equation with a variable coefficient and, using the QHD model and the conventional reductive perturbation method, quantitatively assessed the significance of quantum mechanical effects on compressive and rare active solitons. It has been noted that H plays a crucial role in the production of compressive and uncommon active solitons. The soliton creation stops because of the ion to electron Fermi temperature ratio when a critical value of H is determined based on the wave's phase velocity. IAS with weakly transverse disturbances have been explored by Mushtaq and Khan [11] in a quantum electron-positron-ion plasma using the QHD model. The effects of ion temperature and electron/positron degeneracy on large-amplitude IAS in a concentrated electron-positron-ion plasma have been studied by Akbari-Moghanjoughi [12]. It is demonstrated that the ion-temperature effects play a significant influence in the existence requirements and that the permissible Mach-number range in such plasmas. Additionally, the fundamental distinction between degenerate plasmas with non-relativistic electrons and positrons and those with ultra-relativistic electrons and positrons is discovered. After few days, Chandra et al [13] conducted theoretical research on the analytical and numerical analysis of the linear and nonlinear propagation of electron plasma wave in a two component unmagnified dense quantum plasma with ion streaming. Additionally, they have obtained the KdV equation and demonstrated that, at certain critical values of the quantum diffraction parameter, both compressive and rarefactive solitary waves would be produced in the model plasma. Later, using the derived modified KdV equation, Dip et al. [14] investigated higher-order nonlinearity of the electro-acoustic waves (EAW), specifically ion-acoustic waves (IAW) in an unmagnified, collision-less quantum electron-positron-ion plasma. Using the one-dimensional quantum hydrodynamic model, Paul et al. [15] investigated the nonlinear propagation of IAW in unmagnified quantum (degenerate) plasma in the presence of an ion beam. The RPT is used to derive the K-dV equation. Paul et al. [15] have used the one-dimensional quantum hydrodynamic model to study the nonlinear propagation of IAW in unmagnified quantum (degenerate) plasma in the presence of an ion beam. Using the RPT, the K-dV equation is created. From the K-dV equation, one can get the IAS solution. Depending on the ion beam's velocity, concentration, and temperature levels, the lone waves will either be compressive or refractive. The critical ion beam density for the absence of a single wave has been determined analytically, and the relationship between the ion beam density change with velocity and temperature has been examined using graphical techniques. However, no scientist has yet examined the IADLs in the relativistic degenerate (RD) plasma state. The solitary waves in RD plasmas have been examined by a number of writers, including Shah et al. [18], Masood and Eliason [19], Chandra et al. [20], and Goswami et al. [21]. In order to better understand RD plasmas, which are seen in dense astrophysical objects, authors looked into the solitary waves in RD plasmas. Mamun and Shukla [22] have explored the solitary waves in an ultra-relativistic degenerate (URD) dense plasma using the PRT. Results are investigated in compact astrophysical objects with URD plasma, particularly in white dwarfs. Following that, Mamun and Shukla [23] examined arbitrary amplitude solitary waves and DLs in dense dusty plasma comprising URD ultra-cold electron fluid, inertial ultra-cold ion fluid, negatively charged static dust, etc. Esfandyari-Kalijahi et al. [24] analyse the arbitrary amplitude ion-acoustic solitary waves in plasma with ultra-relativistic or non-relativistic degenerate electrons and positrons concurrently using the SP method. Only compressive solitary waves can propagate in a degenerate plasma state in both ultra-relativistic and non-relativistic conditions. The range of the Mach number and the amplitude of the ion-acoustic solitary waves are strongly influenced by the relativistic degeneracy of positrons and electrons. Roy et al. have studied solitary waves, one type of nonlinear wave propagation, in a

dense plasma comprising URD electrons and positrons, cold mobile inertial ions, and negatively charged static dust. [25] Rahman et al. [26] take into account an RD heated dense electron- ion-positron plasma for the investigation of the linear and nonlinear features of IAW using the RPT. The analysis is extended by creating an equation resembling a pseudo energy balance that includes a Sagdeev-type pseudo-potential for variable amplitude solitary waves. The analysis of the effects of ion (thermal) to electron (Fermi) temperature ratio, positron-to-electron density ratio, and electron relativistic degeneracy parameter is also included in the article. An emerging field of study that has just recently been explored by a few numbers of authors is the DLs of electrostatic waves in URD plasma based on the degenerate electron equation of state. IADLs were investigated by Paul et al. [27] using the SP method in a plasma with degenerate electrons, positrons, and non-degenerate warm ions. The IADLs are shown to be naturally compressive in the excitation state, and the degenerate electrons and positrons in degenerate plasma significantly affect the IADLs. This study examines the IADLs in plasma including cold ions, URD two-temperature electrons and positrons, as well as static negatively charged dust particles. The theoretical analysis was conducted using the SP method and the KBM method. The IADLs in URD plasma are a significant hot research topic because there has been little research on this subject to date, making it simple to come up with fresh ideas. The solutions of IADLs in URD plasma are deduced from the nonlinear equation using the SP method and the KBM method. The profiles of IADLs are drawn and analysed for the various URD electron and positron densities and temperatures. It is evident that in the URD electrons and positrons plasma, degenerate two-temperature electrons and positrons significantly influence the structure of refractive IADLs. Additionally, the widths determined from the structures of IADLs using the KBM and SP methods are compared.

1.1 Basic Equations

This research article takes into account four components of plasma. The plasma is made up of negatively charged static dust particles, inertia-less URD electrons, and cold inertial ion fluid. The ultra-relativistic limit of Chandrasekhar [16,17] has been used to express the degenerate pressure of electrons in terms of density. The following equations describe the nonlinear dynamics of the electrostatic wave in such a URD dense plasma:

$$\frac{\partial n_s}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (n_s u_s) = 0 \text{-----(1)}$$

$$\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial t} + u_i \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x} = -\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} \text{-----(2)}$$

$$n_{ec} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} - \frac{3}{4} \beta_{ec} \frac{\partial n_{ec}^{4/3}}{\partial x} = 0 \text{-----(3)}$$

$$n_{eh} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} - \frac{3}{4} \beta_{eh} \frac{\partial n_{eh}^{4/3}}{\partial x} = 0 \text{-----(4)}$$

$$n_p \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} + \frac{3}{4} \beta_p \frac{\partial n_p^{4/3}}{\partial x} = 0 \text{-----(5)}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2} = \alpha_e n_e - \alpha_p n_p - n_i + \alpha_d \text{-----(6)}$$

where, s = e, p, i denote for electron, positron and ion; velocity u_s is normalized by ion-acoustic speed $c_i = (m_e c^2 / e)^{1/2}$ density n_s is normalized by the equilibrium ion density, the electrostatic potential ϕ is normalized by $m_e c^2 / e$ space variable x and time variable t are normalized by $(m_e c^2 / 4\pi n_{i0} e^2)^{1/2}$ and ion plasma period $(\omega_{pi})^{-1}$;

$$\omega_{pi} = (4\pi n_{i0} e^2 / m_i)^{1/2},$$

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha_{ec} &= (c/m_e n_{ec0}^{1/3}), \\ \alpha_{eh} &= (c/m_e n_{eh0}^{1/3}), \\ \beta_{ec} &= (c/2\pi m_e c) \alpha_{ec}, \\ \beta_{eh} &= (c/2\pi m_e c) \alpha_{eh}, \\ \alpha_p &= \lambda_c n_{p0}^{1/3}, \\ \alpha_p &= (n_{p0}/n_{i0}), \\ \alpha_d &= (z_d n_{d0}/n_{i0}),\end{aligned}$$

n_{e0}, n_{p0}, n_{i0} are the equilibrium densities of electrons, positrons and positive ions ions ; Z_d is number of negative charges of dust particles. According to the concept of neutrality of charge,

$$\alpha_{ec} + \alpha_{eh} - \alpha_p + \alpha_d = 1 \text{-----}(7)$$

Where α_{ec} and α_{eh} are density of degenerate two-temperature electrons; α_p is the density of degenerate positrons and α_d is the density of dust particles in the plasma. So finally, $\alpha_d = 0$, i.e $\alpha_{ec} + \alpha_{eh} = 1 + \alpha_p$

Again it is known to all of us that,

$\xi = x - vt$, where 'v' is the velocity of ion-acoustic wave. Then from the equations (1)-(5) boundary conditions has been obtained. $\varphi \rightarrow 0$ as $\xi \rightarrow \pm\infty$

$$\begin{aligned}n_i &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2\varphi}{V^2}}} \\ n_{ec} &= \left(1 + \frac{\varphi}{3\beta_{ec}}\right)^3\end{aligned}$$

$$n_{eh} = \left(1 + \frac{\varphi}{3\beta_{eh}}\right)^3, n_p = \left(1 - \frac{\varphi}{3\beta_p}\right)^3 \text{-----}(8)$$

where, β_{ec} and β_{eh} are the temperature degenerate electrons at low and high temperatures, β_p is the temperature of degenerate positrons. Now using (8) in (6) we get

$$\frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial \xi^2} = s_1 \varphi + s_2 \varphi^2 + s_3 \varphi^3 \text{-----}(9) \text{ Where}$$

$$s_1 = \left[\frac{\alpha_{ec}}{\beta_{ec}} + \frac{\alpha_{eh}}{\beta_{eh}} + \frac{\alpha_p}{\beta_p} - \frac{1}{V^2}\right] \text{-----}(10a)$$

$$s_2 = \left[\frac{\alpha_{ec}}{3\beta_{ec}^2} + \frac{\alpha_{eh}}{3\beta_{eh}^3} + \frac{\alpha_p}{3\beta_p^3} - \frac{3}{2V^4}\right] \text{-----}(10b)$$

$$s_3 = \left[\frac{\alpha_{ec}}{27\beta_{ec}^3} + \frac{\alpha_{eh}}{27\beta_{eh}^3} + \frac{\alpha_p}{27\beta_p^3} - \frac{5}{2V^6}\right] \text{-----}(10c)$$

2.0 Solution of IADLs using the KBM method:

An integral of (9) satisfying the conditions

$$\frac{d\varphi}{dX} \rightarrow 0, \varphi \rightarrow 0, \text{ as } \xi \rightarrow \pm\infty \text{ is}$$

$$\frac{\varepsilon}{2} \left(\frac{d\varphi}{dX}\right)^2 = \frac{1}{2} s_1 \varphi^2 + \frac{1}{3} s_2 \varphi^3 + \frac{1}{4} s_3 \varphi^4 \text{-----}(11)$$

Here the coordinate has been elongated in accordance with the relation $X = \varepsilon^{1/2} \xi$ -----(12)

In the above equation, ε is a small parameter, $\varepsilon < 1$. It measures how weak the dispersion is. We now make the following perturbation expansions for φ and V .

$$\varphi = \varepsilon \varphi^{(1)} + \varepsilon^2 \varphi^{(2)} + \dots \text{-----}(13a)$$

$$V = V_0 + \varepsilon V^{(1)} + \varepsilon^2 V^{(2)} + \dots \text{-----(13b)}$$

Where V_0 is the linear velocity of ion-acoustic wave. Using with the expansion of V given by (13b) s_1, s_2 and s_3 of Eq.(9) become

$$S_1 = s_1^{(0)} + \varepsilon s_1^{(1)} + \varepsilon^2 s_1^{(2)} + \varepsilon^3 s_1^{(3)} + \dots \text{(14a)}$$

$$S_2 = s_2^{(0)} + \varepsilon s_2^{(1)} + \varepsilon^2 s_2^{(2)} + \dots \text{(14b)}$$

$$S_3 = s_3^{(0)} + \varepsilon s_3^{(1)} + \dots \text{(14c)}$$

$$S_1^{(0)} = 0, S_1^{(1)} = 2\gamma_1^2 V_0 V^{(1)}$$

$$S_1^{(2)} = 2\gamma_1^2 V_0 V^{(2)} + \gamma_1^2 (1 - 4\gamma_1 V_0^2) (V^{(1)})^2,$$

$$S_1^{(3)} = 2\gamma_1^2 V_0 V^{(3)} + 2\gamma_1^3 (1 - 4\gamma_1 V_0^2) V^{(1)} V^{(2)} + 4\gamma_1^3 V_0 (2\gamma_1^2 V_0^2 - 1) (V^{(1)})^3,$$

$$S_2^{(0)} = \gamma_2 - \frac{3}{2} \gamma_1^2,$$

$$S_2^{(1)} = 6\gamma_1^3 V_0 V^{(1)},$$

$$S_2^{(2)} = 6\gamma_1^3 V_0 V^{(2)} + 3\gamma_1^3 (1 - 6\gamma_1 V_0^2) (V^{(1)})^2,$$

$$S_3^{(0)} = \gamma_3 - \frac{5}{2} \gamma_1^3,$$

$$S_3^{(1)} = 15\gamma_1^4 V_0 (V^{(1)})^2,$$

$$\gamma_1 = \frac{\alpha_{ec}}{\beta_{ec}} + \frac{\alpha_{eh}}{\beta_{eh}} + \frac{\alpha_p}{\beta_p} \text{-----(15a)}$$

$$\gamma_2 = \frac{\alpha_{ec}}{3\beta_{ec}^2} + \frac{\alpha_{eh}}{3\beta_{eh}^2} - \frac{\alpha_p}{3\beta_p^2} \text{-----(15b)}$$

$$\gamma_3 = \frac{\alpha_{ec}}{27\beta_{ec}^3} + \frac{\alpha_{eh}}{27\beta_{eh}^3} + \frac{\alpha_p}{27\beta_p^3} \text{-----(15c)}$$

For linear dispersion relation, $(S_1)_0 = S_1^{(0)} = 0$

Therefore,

$$\frac{\alpha_{ec}}{\beta_{ec}} + \frac{\alpha_{eh}}{\beta_{eh}} + \frac{\alpha_p}{\beta_p} = \frac{1}{V_0^2} = \gamma_1 \text{-----(16)}$$

Equation (9) can also be used to determine the solution of IADLs in ultra-relativistic plasma with degenerate two-temperature electrons and positrons. To obtain the solution of IADLs, we make an approximation taking the coefficients of φ^3 of Eq.(9) .

$$V = V_0 + \varepsilon^2 V^{(1)} + \varepsilon^3 V^{(2)} \text{----(17a)}$$

$$X = \varepsilon \xi \text{----(17b)}$$

Using (17a) and (17b) in Eq.(9) ,

$$\frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \left(\frac{d\varphi}{dX}\right)^2 = \frac{1}{2} S_1 \varphi^2 + \frac{1}{3} S_2 \varphi^3 - \frac{1}{4} \varepsilon S_3 \varphi^4 \quad \text{--(18)}$$

Now using S_1, S_2 and S_3 of (9) in (18) and equating the coefficient of ε_4 on both sides we obtain

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{d\varphi^{(1)}}{dX}\right)^2 = \frac{1}{2} S_1^{(1)} (\varphi^{(1)})^2 + \frac{1}{3} S_2^{(0)} (\varphi^{(1)})^3 + \frac{1}{4} S_3^{(0)} (\varphi^{(1)})^4 \text{-----(19)}$$

Now Eq.19 is written in the form

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{d\varphi^{(1)}}{dX}\right)^2 + \Psi(\varphi^{(1)}) = 0 \text{-----(20)}$$

where (Φ) is known as the Sagdeev potential

$$\Psi(\varphi^{(1)}) = -\frac{1}{2} S_1^{(1)} (\varphi^{(1)})^2 - \frac{1}{3} S_2^{(0)} (\varphi^{(1)})^3 - \frac{1}{4} S_3^{(0)} (\varphi^{(1)})^4 \text{-----(21)}$$

Eq. (20) describes the motion of a pseudo particle of unit mass with velocity $d\varphi^{(1)}/dX$ and position $\varphi^{(1)}$ in a potential well $\Psi(\varphi^{(1)})$. The first term of Eq. (20) can be regarded as the kinetic energy of

the pseudo particle where as the second term is the potential energy of same particle at that instant. For the solutions of IADLs, $\Psi(\varphi^{(1)})$ must satisfy the following boundary conditions:

$$(i) \Psi(\varphi^{(1)}) = 0, d\Psi/d\varphi^{(1)} = 0 \text{ and } d^2\Psi/d\varphi^2 < 0 \text{ at } \varphi = 0, \text{-----(22a)}$$

$$(ii) \Psi(\varphi^{(1)}) = 0, d\Psi/d\varphi^{(1)} = 0 \text{ and } d^2\Psi/d\varphi^{(1)2} < 0 \text{ at } \varphi^{(1)} = \varphi_m^{(1)} (\neq 0) \text{---(22b)}$$

$$(iii) \text{ for } 0 < |\varphi^{(1)}| < |\varphi_m^{(1)}| \text{----(22c)}$$

Applying boundary conditions (22a) and (22b) in (21) we obtain

$$\varphi_m = -\frac{2S_2^{(0)}}{3S_3^{(0)}} = -\frac{2(\gamma_2 - 1.5V_0^{-4})}{3(\gamma_3 - 2.5V_0^{-6})} \text{---(23) and}$$

$$(\varphi^{(1)}) = -\frac{S_3^{(0)}}{4} \varphi^{(1)2} (\varphi_m^{(1)} - \varphi^{(1)})^2 \text{---(24a) i.e. } (\varphi^{(1)}) = -\frac{(\gamma_3 - 2.5V_0^{-6})}{4} \varphi^{(1)2} (\varphi_m^{(1)} - \varphi^{(1)})^2 \text{---(24b)}$$

The IADLs solution of (20) satisfying (23) is obtained as

$$\varphi_d = \frac{\varphi_m^{(1)}}{2} (1 - \tanh[\sqrt{\left(\frac{S_3^{(0)}}{8\varphi_m^{(1)}}\right) X}] \text{-----(25a) i.e.}$$

$$\varphi_d = -\frac{1}{3} \frac{(\gamma_2 - 1.5V_0^{-4})}{(\gamma_3 - 2.5V_0^{-6})} (1 - \tanh[\sqrt{\left\{\frac{\gamma_3 - 2.5V_0^{(-6)}}{8\varphi_m^{(1)}}\right\} X}] \text{-----(25b) The width of IADLs is given by}$$

$$W_{dL} = 2\left(\frac{\partial_3^{(0)}}{8|\varphi_m^{(1)}|}\right)^{1/2} \text{-----(26a) i.e. } W_{dL} = 2\left(\frac{\gamma_3 - 2.5V_0^{(-6)}}{8|\varphi_m^{(1)}|}\right)^{1/2} \text{-----(26b)}$$

It is important to note that IADLs in the plasma can only exist for positive value of $S_3^{(0)}$ i.e. $S_3^{(0)} > 0$. From Equations.(23) and (25b) it is clear that the nature of IADLs would be a compressive or rare active depending on the sign of the coefficient of the quadratic nonlinear term. From (23) it is seen that for positive values of $S_2^{(0)}$ rare active IADLs would be excited since of $S_3^{(0)}$ is positive. On the other hand, if $S_2^{(0)}$ is negative a compressive IADLs will be excited

2.1 Solution of IADLs using the SP method

Writing Eq. (9) in the form

$$\frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial \xi^2} = S_1 \varphi + S_2 \varphi^2 + S_3 \varphi^3 = -\frac{d\Psi'}{d\varphi} \text{-----(28)}$$

where $\Psi'(\varphi)$ is known as the Sagdeev potential

$$\Psi'(\varphi) = -\frac{1}{2} S_1 \varphi^2 - \frac{1}{4} S_2 \varphi^3 - \frac{1}{4} S_3 \varphi^4 \text{---(29) For the double layer solutions, } \Psi'(\varphi) \text{ must}$$

additionally satisfy the following boundary conditions:

$$(i) \Psi'(\varphi) = 0, d\Psi'/d\varphi = 0 \text{ and } d^2\Psi'/d\varphi^2 < 0 \text{ at } \varphi = 0 \text{-----(30a)}$$

$$(ii) \Psi'(\varphi) = 0, d\Psi'/d\varphi = 0 \text{ and } d^2\Psi'/d\varphi^2 < 0, \text{at } \varphi = \varphi_{max} (\neq 0) \text{ (30b)}$$

$$(iii) \Psi'(\varphi) < 0, \text{ for } 0 < \varphi < \varphi_m \text{ (30c) applying the boundary conditions we obtain}$$

$$\varphi_m = -\frac{2S_2}{3S_3} \text{-----(31)}$$

$$\text{and } \Psi'(\varphi) = -\frac{S_3}{4} \varphi^2 (\varphi_m - \varphi)^2 \text{-----(32)}$$

The small amplitude IADLs solution of (28) satisfying (31) is obtained as

$$\varphi_D = \frac{1}{2} \varphi_m (1 - \tanh[\sqrt{\left(\frac{S_3}{8\varphi_m}\right) \eta}] \text{-----(33)}$$

The width of IADLs is given by

$$W_{dL} = 2\left(\frac{S_3}{8\varphi_m}\right) \text{-----(34)}$$

It is seen that width of IADLs depends on the plasma parameters e.g. URD two-temperature electrons and positrons. It is to be noted that the IADLs in URD plasma can only exist for positive value of S_3 i.e. $S_3 > 0$.

2.2 Results and Discussion:

At the time of using the KBM method, the solution of electrostatic potential of IADLs is obtained by Eq.(25b) and the width is given by Eq.(26b) in a dusty plasma having ultra-relativistic two-temperature electrons and isothermal positrons. It is to be noted that there are some critical values of α_{ce} and α_p given by (27a) and (27b) for the excitation of the IADLs. The electrostatic potential of IADLs is numerically calculated using a model URD plasma with positrons and two-temperature electrons. The profiles of IADLs are then drawn in varied values of plasma parameters. In addition, using the classic Sagdeev Potential (SP) approach, the electrostatic potential of IADLs in URD plasma with ultra-relativistic two-temperature electrons and positrons is derived from Eq. (45a), and the width is determined from Eq. (46). In this case, for the excitation of the IADLs the critical values of α_{ce} and α_p given by equation (35a) and (35b).

2.3 Profiles of IADLs

Effect of α_{ce} The effect of density of URD electrons on the IADLs is shown in Fig.1(a) and Fig.1(b).

Fig.1(a) plot of Double layer potential (ϕd_j) vs Density of Electron(n_j)(KBM) for different degenerate electron density(α_{ec})

Fig.1(b) plot of Double layer potential (ϕd_j) vs Density of Electron(n_j)(SP) for different degenerate electron density(α_{ec})

Fig.1 (a, b) (Colour online). The profiles of IADLs in URD quantum plasma for different degenerate electron density(α_{ec}). The red, blue and green graphs represent $\alpha_{ec} = 0.045, 0.06, 0.075$; with fixed values of $\beta_{ec} = 0.1, \beta_e = 0.3, \alpha_p = 0.01, \beta_p = 0.1, \alpha_d = 0.85$; Fig.1 (a)-KBM method; Fig.1 (b)-SP method. Fig.1(a) and Fig.1(b) are the profiles of IADLs obtained by KBM method and SP method for different degenerate electron density (α_{ec}) for fixed values of $\beta_{ec} = 0.1, \beta_e = 0.3, \alpha_p = 0.01, \beta_p = 0.1, \alpha_d = 0.85$. From Fig.1 (a) it is seen that the IADL is rarefactive for $\alpha_{ec} = 0.045$ and compressive for $\alpha_{ec} = 0.06, 0.075$.

ii). Effect of β_{ec} : The effect of temperature of URD electrons on the IADLs is shown in Fig.2(a) and Fig.2(b).

Fig.2(a) plot of Double layer potential(ϕd_j) vs Density of Electron(n_j)(KBM) for different degenerate electron temperature β_{ec}

Fig.2(b) plot of Double layer potential(ϕd_j) vs Density of Electron(n_j)(SP) for different degenerate electron temperature β_{ec}

Fig. 2(a,b) (colour online). The profiles of IADLs in URD quantum plasma for different degenerate electron temperature β_{ec} . The red, blue and green graphs represent $\beta_{ec} = 0.02, 0.03, 0.04$; $\alpha_{ec} = 0.0015, \beta_e = 0.3, \alpha_p = 0.01, \beta_p = 0.1$ and $\alpha_d = 0.85$; Fig.2(a)-KBM method; Fig.2(b)-SP method. The profiles of IADLs are shown in Fig.2 for different temperature of degenerate electron (β_{ec}) for fixed values of $\alpha_{ec} = 0.0015, \beta_e = 0.3, \alpha_p = 0.01, \beta_p = 0.1$ and $\alpha_d = 0.85$. Fig.2(a) and Fig.2(b) are the profiles of IADLs obtained by the KBM method and SP method respectively. In Fig.2(a) it is seen that the IADL is rarefactive for $\beta_{ec} = 0.02$ and 0.03 and compressive for $\beta_{ec} = 0.04$

iii). **Effect of α_p** :The effect of density of URD positrons on the IADLs is shown in Fig.3(a) and 3(b).

Fig.3(a) plot of Double layer potential (ϕd_j) vs Density of Electron(n_j)(KBM) for different degenerate positron density (α_p).

Fig.3(b) plot of Double layer potential(ϕd_j) vs Density of Electron(n_j)(SP) for different degenerate positron density (α_p).

Fig. 3(a, b) (colour online). The profiles of IADLs in URD quantum plasma for different degenerate positron density (α_p).The red, blue and green graphs represent $\alpha_p = 0.01, 0.05, 0.09$; $\alpha_{ec} = 0.01, \beta_{ec} = 0.01, \beta_{e\bar{e}} = 0.3, \beta_p = 0.1$ and $\alpha_d = 0.85$; Fig.3(a)-KBM method; Fig.3(b)-SP method.

In Fig.3 the profiles of IADLs are shown for different degenerate positron density (α_p) for fixed values of $\alpha_{ec} = 0.01, \beta_{ec} = 0.01, \beta_{e\bar{e}} = 0.3, \beta_p = 0.1$ and $\alpha_d = 0.85$.The Fig.3 (a) and Fig.3 (b) are the profiles of IADLs obtained by the KBM method and SPmethod respectively. It is seen that the IADL obtained by the KBM method and the SP method are rarefactive. The amplitudes of rarefactive IADLs are decreased with the increase of α_p .

iv) **Effect of β_p** :The effect of temperature of URD positrons on the IADLs is shown in Fig.4 (a) and 4(b).

Fig.4(a) plot of Double layer potential(ϕd_j) vs Density of Electron(n_j)(KBM) for different degenerate positron temperature (β_p).

Fig.4(b) Fig.4(a) plot of Double layer potential(ϕd_j) vs Density of Electron(n_j)(SP) for different degenerate positron temperature (β_p).

Fig. 4(a, b) (colour online). The profiles of IADLs in URD quantum plasma for different degenerate positron temperature (β_p). The red, blue, green, magenta and black graphs represent $\beta_p = 0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04$ and 0.05 ; $\alpha_{ec} = 0.01$, $\beta_{ec} = 0.02$, $\beta_{e\bar{e}} = 0.3$, $\alpha_p = 0.2$ and $\alpha_d = 0.85$; Fig.4(a)-KBM method; Fig.4(b)-SP method.

The profiles of IADLs are shown in Fig.4 for different temperature of degenerate positron (β_p) for fixed values of $\alpha_{ec} = 0.01$, $\beta_{ec} = 0.02$, $\beta_{e\bar{e}} = 0.3$, $\alpha_p = 0.2$ and $\alpha_d = 0.85$. The Fig.4 (a) and Fig.4 (b) are the profiles of IADLs obtained by the KBM method and the SP method respectively. From Fig.4(a) and Fig.4(b) it is seen that the IADLs obtained by KBM method and SP method may be compressive and rarefactive depending on the values of β_p . Fig.4(a) shows that the IADLs are compressive for $\beta_p = 0.01, 0.02$ and 0.03 but it becomes rarefactive for $\beta_p = 0.04$ and 0.05 .

The amplitude of compressive IADL is decreased with the increase of β_p but the amplitude of rarefactive IADL is increased with the increase of β_p on the other hand, Fig.4(b) shows that the IADLs are compressive for $\beta_p = 0.01$ and 0.02 but it becomes rarefactive for $\beta_p = 0.03, 0.04$ and

0.05. The amplitude of compressive IADL is decreased with the increase of β_p but the amplitude of rarefactive IADL is increased with the increase of β_p .

Width of IADLs : The variation of width of IADLs with $\alpha_{ec}, \beta_{ec}, \alpha_p, \beta_p$ are shown in Fig.5, Fig.6, Fig.7 and Fig.8. It is observed that the width of IADLs obtained by the SP method is greater than that obtained by KBM method.

Fig.5 Plot of Double layer Width(Wd_1) vs Degenerate Electron Density (Red for KBM method and Blue for SP Method)

Fig.5 (colour online). Variation of width of IADLs with α_{ec} with fixed values of $\beta_{ec}=0.1$, $\beta_{e\infty}=0.3$, $\alpha_d=0.85$, $\alpha_p=0.01$, $\beta_p=0.1$. The red and blue graphs obtained by the KBM method and SP method respectively.

Fig.6 Plot of Double layer Width(Wd_1) vs Degenerate Electron Temperature (Red for KBM method and Blue for SP Method)

Fig.6 (colour online). Variation of width of IADLs with β_{ec} with fixed values of $\beta_{e\infty}=0.3$, $\alpha_d=0.85$, $\alpha_p=0.01$, $\beta_p=0.1$, $\alpha_{ec}=0.0015$. The red and blue graphs obtained by KBM method and SP method respectively.

Fig.7 Plot of Double layer Width(Wd_1) vs Positron Density
(Red for KBM method and Blue for SP Method)

Fig.7 (colour online). Variation of width of IADLs with positron density (α_p) with fixed values of $\beta_{e\bar{e}}=0.3$, $\alpha_d=0.85$, $\alpha_{ec}=0.01$, $\beta_{ec}=0.01$, $\beta_p=0.1$. The red and blue graphs obtained by the KBM method and the SP method respectively.

Fig.8 Plot of Double layer Width(Wd_1) vs Positron Temperature
(Red for KBM method and Blue for SP Method)

Fig.8 (colour online). Variation of width of IADLs with positron temperature (β_p) with fixed values of $\beta_{e\bar{e}}=0.3$, $\alpha_d=0.85$, $\alpha_{ec}=0.01$, $\beta_{ec}=0.02$, $\alpha_p=0.2$; the red and blue graphs obtained by the KBM method and SP method respectively. From Fig.5 it is seen that the width of IADLs decreases with the increase of degenerate electron density. But, Fig.6 shows that for the increase of degenerate electron temperature the width first decreases up to certain minimum value and then it increases up to certain maximum value after that it decreases again with the increase of degenerate electron temperature. The breadth of IADLs obtained by the KBM approach is lower in both circumstances than that obtained by the SP method due to the increase in degenerate electron density electron temperature. On the other hand, Fig. 7 demonstrates that the width of IADLs grows as degenerate positron density increases. But as can be observed from Fig. 8, as the degenerate positron temperature grows, the width first falls up to a given minimum value, then climbs up to a certain

maximum value, and then decreases once more. It is observed from Fig.5 to Fig.8 that the width of IADLs obtained by the SP method is greater than those obtained by KBM method.

2.4 Conclusion :

This study presents a theoretical investigation of the IADLs in a dusty plasma made up of cold ions, negatively charged dust particles, ultra-relativistic degenerate two-temperature electrons, and positrons. The solution of double layers is obtained using the approach based on the expansion of Sagdeev potential up to the third-order and the conventional reductive perturbation method. For the KBM method, we start from an integrated form of the system of governing equations in terms of the pseudo-potential considering higher order nonlinear and dispersive effects. With the SP approach, the electrostatic potential and wave phase velocity are not expanded in order to achieve the solution of IADLs using the traditional Sagdeev potential method. Most important and significant results on the IADLs in dusty plasma having cold ions and ultra-relativistic two-temperature electrons and isothermal positrons are: It is possible to excite the refractive and compressive IADLs in URD plasma depending on the values of plasma parameters, i.e. $\alpha_{ec}, \beta_{ec}, \alpha_p$ and β_p .

Effect of URD electron density (α_{ec}): The IADLs by the KBM method is rarefactive for $\alpha_{ec} = 0.045$ and compressive for $\alpha_{ec} = 0.06, 0.075$ when other plasma parameters have fixed values. The amplitude of compressive IADL is decreased with the increase of α_{ec} . But, in similar plasma the IADLs by the Sagdeev potential method are rarefactive for $\alpha_{ec} = 0.045, 0.06$ and 0.075 and the amplitudes of rarefactive IADLs are increased with the increase of α_{ec} .

Effect of URD electron temperature (β_{ec}): The IADLs by the KBM method is rarefactive for $\beta_{ec} = 0.02, 0.03$ and compressive for $\beta_{ec} = 0.04$. The amplitude of rarefactive IADLs is decreased with the increase of β_{ec} . But, in similar plasma the IADLs by the Sagdeev potential method are rarefactive for $\beta_{ec} = 0.02, 0.03$ and 0.04 . The amplitudes of rarefactive IADLs are increased with the increase of β_{ec} .

Effect of URD positron density (α_{ec}): The IADLs by KBM method and SP method are rarefactive for $\alpha_p = 0.01, 0.05, 0.09$ when the values of $\alpha_{ec} = 0.01, \beta_{ec} = 0.01, \beta_{eh} = 0.3, \beta_p = 0.1$ and $\alpha_d = 0.85$.

Width of IADLs : The width of IADLs obtained using the KBM approach and the SP method in the plasma is affected differently by URD electrons and positrons. The most crucial thing to note in this paper is that almost all papers present the research of IADLs utilising the reductive perturbation approach and the SP method. However, the research of IADLs in plasma with URD two-temperature electrons and positrons is presented in this paper, and the outcomes from using the KBM approach and the SP method have been contrasted. Because each mathematical technique makes a different set of assumptions, it is observed that the width and structure of IADLs change between the KBM method and the SP method.

In the current experiment, we assumed that the concentrations of URD two-temperature electrons and positrons were high and that the densities of dust particles were low and significantly lower. For the study of IADLs in URD single temperature electrons and positrons, however, the density of dust particles should be taken into account as being high, i.e., we must take into account a dense dusty plasma. Positrons and two-temperature electrons are known to make up the multispecies composition of space plasmas. Therefore, the current findings on the IADLs may be helpful for the study of nonlinear wave processes in numerous space plasma environments where the degenerate electrons and positrons of ultra-relativity exist. It is important to be mentioned that the nonlinear propagation of waves in an electron-ion-positron (e-i-p) plasma is important [28-32] due to relevance on the wave processes in galactic nuclei [33], pulsar magnetosphere [34], polar caps of neutron stars [35] etc.

FIGURE CAPTIONS: Fig. 1(a, b). The profiles of IADLs in URD quantum plasma for different degenerate electron density (α_{ec}). The red, blue and green graphs represent $\alpha_{ec} = 0.045, 0.06, 0.075$; with fixed values of $\beta_{ec}=0.1, \beta_{eh}=0.3, \alpha_p=0.01, \beta_p=0.1, \alpha_d=0.85$;

Fig.1 (a)-KBM method;

Fig.1 (b)-SP method.

Fig. 2(a, b). The profiles of IADLs in URD quantum plasma for different degenerate electron temperature β_{ec} . The red, blue and green graphs represent $\beta_{ec} = 0.02, 0.03, 0.04$; $\alpha_{ec}=0.0015, \beta_{eh}=0.3, \alpha_p=0.01, \beta_p=0.1$ and $\alpha_d=0.85$;

Fig.2(a)-KBM method;

Fig.2(b)-SP method.

Fig. 3(a,b). The profiles of IADLs in URD quantum plasma for different degenerate positron density (α_p). The red, blue and green graphs represent $\alpha_p = 0.01, 0.05, 0.09$; $\alpha_{ec}=0.01, \beta_{ec}=0.01, \beta_{eh}=0.3, \beta_p=0.1$ and $\alpha_d=0.85$;

Fig.3(a)-KBM method;

Fig.3(b)-SP method.

Fig. 4(a,b). The profiles of IADLs in URD quantum plasma for different degenerate positron temperature (β_p). The red, blue, green, magenta and black graphs represent $\beta_p = 0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04$ and 0.05 ; $\alpha_{ec}=0.01, \beta_{ec}=0.02, \beta_{eh}=0.3, \alpha_p=0.2$ and $\alpha_d=0.85$;

Fig.4(a)-KBM method;

Fig.4(b)-SP method.

Fig.5. Variation of width of IADLs with α_{ec} with fixed values of $\beta_{ec}=0.1, \beta_{eh}=0.3, \alpha_d=0.85, \alpha_p=0.01, \beta_p=0.1$. The red and blue graphs obtained by KBM method and SP method respectively.

Fig.6. Variation of width of IADLs with β_{ec} with fixed values of $\beta_{eh}=0.3, \alpha_d=0.85, \beta_p=0.01, \beta_p=0.1, \alpha_{ec}=0.0015$. The red and blue graphs obtained by KBM method and SP method respectively.

Fig.7. Variation of width of IADLs with positron density (α_p) with fixed values of $\beta_{eh}=0.3, \alpha_d=0.85, \alpha_{ec}=0.01=0.01, \beta_{ec}=0.01, \beta_p=0.1$. The red and blue graphs obtained by KBM method and SP method respectively.

Fig.8. Variation of width of IADLs with positron temperature (β_p) with fixed values of $\beta_{eh}=0.3, \alpha_d=0.85, \alpha_{ec}=0.01, \beta_{ec}=0.02, \alpha_p=0.2$;

The red and blue graphs obtained from KBM method and SP method respectively.

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